

MODELING AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF THE VARTM PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process is broadly used for producing large-scale and thin-walled fiber reinforced polymer composite (FRPC) components. The characteristics of the resin flow and the fibrous preform deformation, e.g., thickness variations, significantly affect the cycle time and quality of final products. To predict and simulate the process in a computationally efficient manner, we treat the 3-D resin flow as in-plane flow; and limit the preform deformation only in the normal of the mold surface. A vacuum infusion experiment is carried out for calibration and validation. The comparison shows a good match between the simulation and the experiment results. The present model efficiently predicts realistic results of the preform thickness variation and the flow front location.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lawrence JM et al. [1] noticed the *lubrication effect*, i.e., a sudden drop of the preform thickness that is induced by the pressure discontinuity at the flow front. Tackitt and Walsh [2] characterized the phenomenon of the preform thickness increase in resin saturated regions, viz., *spring-back mechanism*. Those two mechanisms can represent the main phenomena of the preform thickness variation during the VARTM process. Many studies from different fields have been done to study and model the preform deformation. Jeffrey A. Acheson et al. [3] suggested a 1-D model to identify the coupling between the fiber compaction and resin saturation from a parametric study. M Akif Yalcinkaya and E Murat Sozer [4] observed that in the wetted upstream region, the thickness and the effective permeability increase with time. They designed the experiment to validate the analytical formulation from [5], which modeled the preform compaction during the VARTM process. Wu Da and Larsson Ragnar [6] reported a model based on the porous media theory that reveals the pressure discontinuity at the flow front.

To study the thickness variation of the fibrous preform in the VARTM process, we prepare a vacuum infusion experiment on a non-crimp fabrics panel. The flow development during the process can be observed by visual inspections, and the deformation of the preform is monitored by the digital image correlation system. On the other hand, a mathematical model of the VARTM process is also developed. Based on the observation of the preform deformation in the process, some assumptions have been made to simplify the complicate fluid/solid interaction problem. An infusion experiment also validates the accuracy of the model.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

The non-crimp fabrics (NCFs) that fabricated from Toho Tenax[®] HTS45 E23 carbon fiber bundles are used in the experiment to assemble preforms. To get rid of the influence of curing, we choose the rapeseed oil to replace the usually used thermoset resin. The properties of the materials used in the experiment are listed in Table 1.

Item	Identification	Value
fabric	superficial density	812 g/m^2
	longitudinal permeability, \hat{k}_{11}	$11.5 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$
	transverse permeability, \hat{k}_{22}	$12.6 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$
	fiber volume fraction, n_0^s	0.411
resin	density, ρ^l	930 kg/m^3
	viscosity, μ_l	$0.067 \text{ P} \cdot \text{s}$

Table 1: Fabric and resin properties.

2.2 Experiment setup and process

The experiment setup is depicted in Figure 1. First, eight layers of NCFs are stacked following a $[(-45/45)/(90/0)]_s$ layup as the fibrous preform ($22 \text{ cm} \times 38 \text{ cm}$) on an aluminum mold ($1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$). Then, on top of the preform, a layer of peel ply is placed. Because the preform is thin (6.5 mm) compared with other dimensions, the distribution layer is not needed. A helical tube is placed at the inlet side of the mold. The inlet tube connects to the resin reservoir, and the outlet tube is connected to the vacuum pump. Finally, the mold is covered by a vacuum bag and sealed by tacky tapes around all edges of the preform. When the VARTM experiment setup is ready, the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system from GOM Aramis® is installed on top of the VARTM setup to carry out the in-situ monitoring during the infusion process.

When the experiment starts, the inlet valve is clamped, and the outlet valve is open to pump out the air. The vacuum stays at 32 mbars for 15 minutes until infusion starts. Once the vacuum is ready, the resin flows into the mold from the reservoir under the atmospheric pressure. In the meanwhile, the DIC is monitoring the flow development and the deformation of the preform. After the whole preform is saturated, the vacuum is kept for 30 minutes.

Figure 1: The VARTM experiment setup schematic (left) and the infusion arrangement (right).

3 MATHEMATICAL MODEL AND NUMERICAL SIMULATION

3.1 In-plane Darcy flow

The resin flow is modeled by two equations that contain the primary variables: 1) resin/gas mixture fluid pressure p and 2) saturation degree ξ . First, the pressure equation derived from mass conservation of the solid-fluid mixture as

$$\frac{\dot{J}}{J} + \frac{\rho^l - \rho^g}{\rho^f} n^f \dot{\xi} + \frac{n^f(1-\xi)}{\rho^f} \dot{\rho}^g + \frac{1}{\rho^f} \nabla \cdot (\rho^f \mathbf{v}^{df}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

and second, the saturation equation that represents the evolution of the saturation degree

$$n^f \dot{\xi} + \xi \frac{\dot{J}}{J} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}^{dl} = 0, \quad (2)$$

The J in Equation 1 and 2 is the Jacobian of the deformation tensor, the ρ^l and ρ^g is the density of the resin and gas, respectively; the ρ^f denotes the density of the resin/gas mixture fluid. n^f and n^s denote the volume fractions of the fluid and the fiber, respectively. Darcy's velocity \mathbf{v}^{df} and \mathbf{v}^{dl} can be determined from Darcy's law as

$$\mathbf{v}^{dl} = -\mathbf{K}^l \nabla p^l, \text{ and } \mathbf{v}^{df} = -\mathbf{K}_p^f \nabla p - \mathbf{K}_\xi^f \nabla \xi, \quad (3)$$

where the \mathbf{K}^l , \mathbf{K}_p^f and \mathbf{K}_ξ^f are permeability related terms defined in [6].

As to thin-walled components, the through-thickness flow can be ignored. Thus, we introduce the in-plane projection operator to convert 3-D variables to the in-plane variables. For instance, the in-plane flow velocity can be expressed as $\bar{\mathbf{v}} = \bar{\mathbf{I}} \cdot \mathbf{v}$, where $\bar{\mathbf{I}}$ is the projection tensor, and \mathbf{v} is the full 3-D flow velocity. By using the in-plane gradient operator $\bar{\nabla}$, the volume integration in the domain B_0 can be transferred to a surface integration on Ω_0 , e.g., Equation 4. So that the 3-D flow problem can be converted as a 2-D problem.

$$\int_{B_0} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} dB = h_0 \int_{\Omega_0} \bar{\nabla} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}} d\Omega. \quad (4)$$

3.2 Preform stretch

By the feature of the plastic membrane, the deformation can be simplified and described by the normal stretch $\lambda = h/h_0$, where h is the thickness of the deformed preform, and h_0 is the un-deformed preform thickness. As Figure 2 shows, the position vector pointing to the preform top surface can be expressed as $\Phi + h_0 \lambda \mathbf{N}$. Thus, when $\lambda = 1$, it implies that the preform is undeformed; the compression and expansion can also be identified by $\lambda < 1$ and $\lambda > 1$, respectively. Based on this assumption, we derived the formulation of the stretch from the linear momentum balance equation as

$$\lambda = \left(1 + \frac{p^a - p}{k^s E (n_0^s)^m} \right)^{-\frac{1}{m}}, \quad (5)$$

where m and $k^s E$ are the parameters of the packing law proposed in [7], n_0^s is the initial fiber volume fraction and p^a is the applied atmospheric pressure.

Figure 2: The definition of (un-)deformed configurations of the thin-walled preform and the mapping relating to the inertial Cartesian frame.

3.3 Boundary and initial values of the numerical simulation

To simulate the experiment described in Section 2, we design the numerical simulation as follows. The inlet infusion pressure is set to $p_0 = 1$ atm, and the corresponding saturation degree is given as $\xi_0 = 1.0$. For the outlet, the pressure p_1 equals to 32 mbars, and there is no flux of saturation degree across all edges of the preform except the inlet, i.e., $\partial_x \xi = 0$. Regarding the initial values, the initial saturation degree is determined by ${}^0\xi = \xi(\mathbf{x}, 0) = 0.001$, and the initial pressure is given as ${}^0p = p(\mathbf{x}, 0) = 32$ mbars.

Besides the parameters listed in Table 1, the parameters used in the simulation, e.g., packing law factor $k^s E$, packing law exponent m , capillary pressure constant n_b and the entry pressure p^{ent} are calibrated from the experiment. Table 2 summaries all parameters used in this simulation.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As illustrated in Section 2, the preform stays vacuum for a while before the infusion starts. At this stage, the preform is compacted due to the inside/outside pressure difference. We choose the preform thickness at this moment as the reference; in other words, the vertical displacement of the preform equals to zeros. As shown in Figure 3, the vertical displacements measured by the DIC at different times are plotted. Below the DIC images, the contour plots of the simulation are placed. We draw red dash lines to mark up the alignments between DIC images and simulation contours. At time 29 seconds, the DIC image shows a red band, which is also appearing in the contour plot. The dashed line indicates the good match of the expansion (*spring-back*) region of the preform between the experiment and simulation. After time 60 seconds, the compaction band shows up, which reflects the *lubrication effect*. The distance between the two dashed lines identifies the width of the lubrication effect zone. As the flow front moving forward, the expansion band extends slowly wider. The increase of the width and depth of the compaction band can be also observed during the process.

Parameters	Unit	Identification	Value
n_0^s	-	fiber volume fraction	0.411
\hat{k}_{11}	m^2	longitudinal permeability	11.5×10^{-11}
\hat{k}_{22}	m^2	transverse permeability	12.6×10^{-11}
ρ^l	kg/m^3	resin density	930
μ_l	$Pa \cdot s$	resin viscosity	6.696×10^{-2}
μ_g	$Pa \cdot s$	gas viscosity	1.983×10^{-5}
n_b	-	capillary pressure constant	2.4581
p^{ent}	Pa	entry pressure	1.541×10^5
m^g	kg/mol	gas molar mass	2.897×10^{-2}
R	$J/K \cdot mol$	ideal gas constant	8.314
T	K	absolute temperature	293
$k^s E$	Pa	packing law factor	1.974×10^6
m	-	packing law exponent	7

Table 2: Parameters of the fibrous preform, resin, and environment.

The different bands of deformation of the preform are represented in Figure 3. Now we plot the preform from side to show the deformed longitudinal profiles. In Figure 4, the red curves show the vertical displacement from the simulation results; the blue shadow indicates the plus/negative errors from experiment data. The displacement at the inlet is constrained to zero due to the boundary condition. A global peak appears behind the inlet, followed by the global trough. After the global trough, the displacement curve jumps up a small value and forms a local peak. Concerning Figure 3, the global peak reflects the spring-back (red band); the global trough indicates the lubrication effect (green/blue band). Figure 4 also shows the blue shadow locates very close to the red curve, which tells that the differences between the simulation and the experiment are limited small.

Figure 3: The preform vertical displacement during the experiment (above) and the simulation (below) of the VARTM process.

Figure 4: The preform longitudinal profiles from the simulation (red curve) and the plus/negative errors from the experiment (blue shadow).

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have developed a model of the VARTM process for the thin-walled fiber reinforced polymer composite material components in this paper. Based on the theory of porous media, we model the interaction between the resin/gas fluid and the solid fiber as porous media problem. By virtual of this treatment, the complexity of the solid/fluid interaction problem is simplified dramatically to the transportation of the resin inside the porous preform.

Moreover, the further assumption on the ignorance of the through-thickness flow has been made. This assumption helps to convert the 3-D problem to a 2-D problem that significantly reduces the degree of freedom of the problem. The preform is then modeled by the shell-like elements, which replace the solid elements. In addition, the normal stretch is used to describe the preform thickness variation. By means of all assumptions and simplifications, the model dramatically reduces the computational cost.

What's more, both the *lubrication effect* and the *spring-back mechanism* are witnessed in the simulation and experiment. The typical Peak-Trough-Peak deformed preform profile is found from both cases, which is also reported in [4] and [8]. Good agreements have been observed between the experiment and simulation results. The study in this paper provides a computational assistant tool for industries to simulate and predict the VARTM process of the production of the thin-walled fiber reinforced polymer composite material components.

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